

QUIZ

LAST NAME: Audace

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PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord for office 365 ProPlus on Windows 10 Pro

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What are the three factors that make a good quality academic essay?**
 - Written in American English, following all punctuations rules, and supported by facts from literature review.
 - Evidence support provided, the proper references, and well structured; that is the presence of the introduction, the main body and the conclusion.¹**
 - Based on primary data only, the methodology should be clearly defined, and the analysis of findings presented.
 - Following the Chicago Manual of Style, good English, properly referenced.
- 2. When is it appropriate to paraphrase the words from the source in the academic research context?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

- When you need only the general point of a passage.
 - When you do not want to cite the source.
 - When you have use too many direct quotations before.
 - When you can represent what a source says more clearly or pointedly than it does.²**
3. **What is a research argument according to the eighth edition of the Turabian Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations?**
- A process to develop and address research questions with support by reasons and evidence from research findings and literature.³**
 - A researcher's response to opposing views.
 - A researcher's proposed solution to the research problem.
 - A research methodology.
4. **Who among the following student is guilty of plagiarism?**
- A student cites every source quoted.
 - A student paraphrases and cites a source.
 - A student uses a source in its exact words without putting them in quotation marks or block quotation.⁴**
 - A student has not used any external sources.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 32.

5. **In which fields the Notes-bibliography citation style is most commonly used according to the eighth edition of the Turabian Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations?**
- Mathematics.
 - Humanities and some social sciences.**⁵
 - Natural sciences.
 - Physical sciences.
6. **Which of the following basic forms of parenthetical citations is correct in the Author-dates citation style as per the eighth edition of the Turabian Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations?**
- Author's full name Year of Publication.
 - Author's last name, Year of Publication, Page number(s).
 - Author's last name Year of Publication, Page number(s).**⁶
 - Author's First name Year of Publication, Page number(s).
7. **In which of the following cases a period should not be placed at the end of a sentence?**
- At the end of a chapter title.**⁷

³ Ibid., 36-42.

⁴ Ibid., 51.

⁵ Ibid., 87.

⁶ Ibid., 129.

⁷ Ibid., 173.

- At the of a declarative statement.
- At the end of an indirect question.
- At the end of an imperative statement.

8. **What are the common main parts of a research proposal?**

- Preface, Introduction, and methodology.
- Introduction, literature review, and methodology.⁸**
- Front matter, text, and back matter.
- Introduction, methodology, and analysis of findings.

9. **In which of the following dissertation chapters can the researcher express his/her own views about the research findings?**

- Literature review.
- Research Methodology.
- Analysis and interpretation of findings.⁹**
- Presentation of findings.

10. **What are the internal working languages of the European Commission?**

- Dutch, Spanish, and English.
- Irish, Polish, and French.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Volpe F. Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 18-20.

⁹ Ibid., 128-129.

- English, French, and German.**¹⁰
- French, Italian, and German.

¹⁰ Cooper Tim, Fallas John, Flaherty Francis, Jones John, Martin Tim, Stockwell Jonathan, Townsend Julia and Workman Peter, *English style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Seventh ed. (Directorate-General for Translation: European Commission, 2011), 75.

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Tim C., John F., Francis, John J., Tim M., Jonathan, Julia and Peter Workman. *English style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Seventh ed. Directorate-General for Translation: European Commission, 2011.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.